

Balancing Act: Exploring the Challenges and Triumphs of Special Program in Sports (SPS) Coaches in Public Schools

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Publication Date: May 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15781007

Abstract

This study explored how coaches balance teaching and coaching careers, challenges, and triumphs experienced by Special Program in Sports (SPS) coaches in public schools. The main thrust of this study was to discover the different emerging themes of coaches' experiences that surfaced and were derived from the in-depth interviews. This used an intrinsic research design to generate valuable and needed data. Participants were briefed on their roles before the interview commenced. Findings revealed the following themes: how coaches balanced their coaching and teaching; effective time management and scheduling, reciprocal influence and integration of teaching and coaching practices, employing conflict resolution and prioritization strategies, using institutional and collegial support, and dual role management through strategic planning and

collaboration. On the other hand, it was also found that, although teacher-coaches experienced the following challenges in coaching, they still managed to perform their dual role. The challenges of coaches were time management & scheduling constraints, limited resources and infrastructure, students' motivation, discipline, skills development challenges, administrative policy constraints, and socio-economic and inclusion challenges. Finally, triumphs encountered by coaches were competitive success and achievement, holistic athlete development, personal growth, and innovative coaching practices leading to success. It is therefore recommended that DepEd officials and other stakeholders continue to support the teacher-coaches and student-athletes.

Keywords: *Challenges, triumphs, coaches, teaching and coaching*

INTRODUCTION

Professionals who conduct coaching thoroughly understand the physical activities, abilities, and methods necessary to impart that information to others. This calls for proficiency in creating conditioning experiences to improve performance and practice scenarios that encourage learning. This activity is needed to discover potential champions by unleashing the innate skills and talents of the student-athletes. It is claimed that the role of coaches is to help players reach their full potential, specifically children's athletes.

In Europe, coaching children's athletes is recognized as having low status and public value compared to high-performance athletes. For this reason, coaches are underpaid and the least remunerated. However, European sports are widely known as recreational activities among students, specifically during free periods or after classes (Veega, 2022). In the 2021-22 school year, according to data from the National Federation of State High School Associations, the sport with the most male participants nationally was 11-player football, with 973,792 participants. It was outdoor track and field for girls, with 456,697 participants (Riser-Kositsky et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, the Philippines' Department of Education issued DepEd Order No. 25, Series of 2015, also known as Implementing Guidelines on the Special Program in Sports (SPS), which provides information and guidelines for the admission of learners in the program. As experienced by the coaches, implementing a Special Program in Sports in the Philippines encountered numerous challenges. Ordonez (2022) discovered that one of the problems in coaching students is insufficient funds. Remas (2023) cited in his study that discovering potential athletes can be a great challenge to coaches without sufficient funds, since every sport needs a standard venue and equipment. In addition, coaching is a profession; it only means that coaches must be compensated.

Sto. Nino National High School is one of the pioneering schools in implementing SPS, and problems arise every year. One of the coach's issues is the admission of potential students for the program. Galve (2023) emphasized that this can be attributed to the enrolment procedure since no examination tool examined the potentialities of the student-entrants of the program. As observed by Salazar (2024), another issue is the lack of a sports venue; while it is one of the requirements of the application for the offering of SPS, the venue is not provided during validation, and the school used one of its classrooms as a venue for indoor game table tennis. Due to the increasing number of enrollees in the school, the playing venue was used as a classroom (Calmerin, 2024).

Thus, this study explored the challenges and triumphs of the coaches and their struggles in balancing teaching careers and coaching athletes in the public schools offering Special Programs in Sports. This study gives worthy insights how coaching is experienced and implemented in the schools of Department of Education, especially in public schools. Through thorough investigation, valuable data can be gleaned from the coach-participants, which may provide a clearer picture of what is happening in the field and may provide feedback or positive reinforcement from the higher-ups of the agency and the community.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored to Scott Cappos's Theory on Coaching. Scott Cappos, a Husker Team coach on throws in 2014, developed this theory and joined the Nebraska Team in 2021. His experience as a coach developed the theory. His theory emphasized the vital function of modeling, motivation, and encouragement. One needs a model for him to mimic, a motivation that can drive one to do coaching, and encouragement to keep coaching (Forro, 2024). Coaching experience has played an important role in making coaching effective and efficient. Lancer and Eatough (2018) explained that coaches' experiences in their field of sport gradually made them master the craft.

Furthermore, Self-Determination Theory greatly considers the importance of intrinsic motivation, which is driven by fulfilling three fundamental psychological needs: relatedness, competence, and autonomy. This intrinsic motivation is important in establishing the drive to things, Singh et al. (2021) clarified. This

suggests that effective coaching is achieved when prior experience is related to coaching to attain competence and autonomy. At the same time, Social Cognitive Theory emphasizes the role of modeling, observation, and social interaction. Thus, these three theories on coaching sports are related to one another through experience. Experience that provides experiential learning is important to understanding the concept of coaching. Although these theories focus on different attributes, they have something in common: experience, which can be a great thing for making these coaches master their field of game or event being coached.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram on the Theoretical Framework of the Study

Limitations of the Study

This study focused on the experiences of Special Program in the Arts coaches in balancing teaching and coaching careers, challenges, and triumphs as coaches of student-athletes. Specifically, participants were chosen considering the criteria set by the researcher for better and more reliable results. The study utilized participants who had been coaching for three (3) or more years, had been coaching the same event for three (3) or more years, were recognized by the school or division as a coach for a particular event or sport, and had brought student-athletes to the regional or national level. Facefacts (2023) emphasized that researchers can have greater confidence in the data they obtain when recruiting participant coaches in the South Cotabato Division, which can meet the qualification standard.

Moreover, a more thorough analysis was made possible, allowing researchers to draw precise conclusions and anchor their decisions on the data. The overall quality and validity of the research findings were heightened by the truthful opinions of stealthily chosen participants. Participants were expected to tell their beautiful stories as coaches in the Division of South Cotabato public schools. Specifically, this study transpired in the three (3) schools under the said school division, namely Sto. Nino National High School, Libertad National High School, and Banga National High School. These schools have been offering a Special Program in Sports since 2020. The participants were interviewed through a validated interview guide with questions, and the interviews took place in the second week of March 2025.

Statement of the Problem

This study explored coaches' experiences coaching student-athletes in public schools' Special Programs in Sports. Particularly, the researcher conducted a study in three (3) public schools in the South Cotabato Division that offer Special Programs in Sports. These schools are considered pioneers in the implementation of SPS. It answered the following research questions:

1. How do coaches balance coaching and teaching careers?
2. What challenges do coaches face in coaching Special Program in Sports student-athletes in the public schools?
3. What are the triumphs of coaches in coaching Special Program in Sports student-athletes in the public schools?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the intrinsic study design of qualitative research to discover and describe the experiences of the Special Program in Sports coaches in public schools, particularly coaches in schools in the Department of Education in South Cotabato Division currently offering the Special Program in Sports. Pretorius (2023) mentioned that as people's experiences were acknowledged as valuable sources of information, digging and understanding personal experiences is becoming increasingly significant. Individual experiences can shed light on the intricacies of human endeavors and offer unique perspectives on historical, social, and cultural disciplines. Therefore, this study tried to discover the challenges and struggles of the coaches and the triumphs in coaching student-athletes as part of their odyssey in the Department of Education.

Participants of the Study

The three (3) participating schools involved in this study were Sto. Nino National High School, Libertad National High School and Banga National High School. Four (4) participants of the study came from Sto. Nino National High School. 2 participants came Libertad National High School and the 2 others came from Banga National High School. Generally, the participants were hidden in a pseudonym in response of the Data Privacy Act Law of 2012. **An act protecting individual personal information in information and communications systems in the government and the private sector, creating for this purpose a national privacy commission and other purposes.**

Sampling Technique

The researcher employed a purposive sampling technique for the study. Through this technique, participants were purposively chosen. The researcher used this technique when they had the idea of what characteristics were needed to be a potential participant (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023), or sample participants must meet the criteria set by the researcher to gather reliable data based on the experience and consistency of the results. For a clearer understanding of how the participants were chosen, these criteria must be met: (1) Had been coaching for three (3) or more years; (2) Had been coaching the same event for three

(3) or more years; (3) Recognized by the school or division as coach for a particular event or sport, and (4) Had brought student-athletes to Regional or National Level.

Anchored to these criteria, the identification of participants was made easy through the help of the School Sports Coordinators of every school of the study participants, for they knew well the coaches who met the criteria imposed. To sum up, there were eight (8) participants who played an important part in the completion of this piece of work.

Research Instruments

The researcher prepared interview guide questions and a voice recorder apparatus to capture every interview detail. Lived experiences were extracted from the participants up to the saturation point. Beames et al. (2021) emphasized that research on lived experiences provides valuable data that can influence and improve the caliber and applicability of scientific reviews. There were numerous advantages to combining these two apparently disparate study approaches for the academic community and those who have lived the experience.

Moreover, the dynamic scenery of the interview can become more credible by using images to present the actual scenario, particularly photo-elicitation, which empowers participants by involving them actively in the process, making them the experts, and providing the researcher with more insight into participant viewpoints.

In addition to avoiding using survey questionnaires and other potentially culturally biased research tools, photo-elicitation provides individuals who were not verbally fluent with an additional means of effectively expressing themselves. It also treats participants as equal, allowing them to reflect and choose how they wish to represent themselves visually. Thus, photo-elicitation has its roots in an inquiry-based methodology that aligns with the larger participatory action research approach and draws from Paulo Freire's critical pedagogy (Cleland et al., 2021).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher outlined a procedure to guide her actions when gathering data. This process is composed of stages that organize the collection of accurate data.

Stage 1: Secure Graduate School Permit to Conduct Study. To commence the study formally, a permit was requested from the Graduate School of Sultan Kudarat State University. This step ensures the legality of the study's conduct.

Step 2. Develop interview guide questions. Anchored on the statement of the problem raised in this study, interview guide questions were made to simplify the specific questions to create themes or subjects.

Step 3. Validate interview guide questions. Experts in qualitative research were needed to validate the interview guide questions. This was to produce quality questions that yielded quality answers for the problem statements.

Step 4. Seek Approval of the Division Superintendent. While schools were normally under the jurisdiction of the higher-ups, it is just right to inform the Division Office that a study is being conducted in two (2) of its schools.

Step 5. Ask Permission of the School Heads. This study's respondents were teachers. A leader who governed them was called the school head. It is then proper to ask their permission to use their time and expertise to validate the evaluation and assessment tool developed.

Step 6. Conduct of Interview. To gather factual information and arrive at the best first-hand information, the interview must be casual and like a normal conversation. In this manner, participants feel the freedom for easy flow of ideas.

Step 7. Transcribing the Recorded Voice. When voice statements were translated into visible letters and words, such as mannerisms, adlibs, and the like, themes were easily identified.

Step 8. Grouping the Statements into Themes and/or Subthemes / Qualitative research is usually presented into themes, which group statements that share the same ideas or thoughts.

Step 9. Analysis and Interpretation of Data Gathered. The researcher employed qualitative knowledge to describe statements of the same theme. Thus, data were presented and described through descriptions.

Ethical Considerations

Cocciattolo (2015) reminds us of the importance of preserving the welfare of the participants to protect them from pressure and stress. Hence, the participant's identity should remain in the shed of darkness. The conduct of this study was properly channeled to avoid problems or inconvenience. It was a must that the researcher should inform the research committee members of the college where they were enrolled for information dissemination. After seeking their signatures, the letter was also sent to the office of the Department of Education Regional Director, Schools Division Superintendent, and school heads of the schools where the study was conducted. After approval, another letter was also handed to all the study participants to request their willingness to participate in this study. Then, the interview commenced with a reminder that all the information they were about to disclose was used for the research and nothing else, and their identity remains confidential.

RESULTS and DSICUSSION

Table 1. Themes on How Do Coaches Balance Coaching and Teaching Careers

Emerging Themes	Clustered Themes	Codes	Significant Statements
1.Effective Time Management and Scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -organizing daily tasks -planning schedules ahead -following strict time management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -time management; -schedule; -organizing; -planning 	<p>"Time management and creative teaching strategies, Ma'am." - Coach 1</p> <p>"..., time management planning to balance coaching and being a classroom teacher at the same</p>

			<p>time." -Coach 2</p> <p>"Ahhmm, of course, you can't just be coaching all the time and teaching all the time... at least I was able to use that time, and it wasn't affected by the child's class hours." -Coach 3</p> <p>"So, of course, the best thing is time management. If you have time management, you can do more things as one... ." -Coach 4</p>
2. Reciprocal Influence and Integration of Teaching and Coaching Practices	<p>–integration of teaching experience into coaching</p> <p>–using demonstration and modeling</p> <p>–motivating through teaching strategies</p>	<p>-teaching;</p> <p>-demonstrate;</p> <p>-model;</p> <p>-motivate;</p> <p>-communication</p>	<p>"... my experience as a teacher influenced my coaching methods or vice versa by sharing with them what makes a good and a successful athlete." -Coach 5</p> <p>"Teaching helps me communicate better with my athletes and understand their individual styles..." -Coach 6</p> <p>"In my long years of teaching and coaching, they are almost the same." -Coach 7</p> <p>"My experience as a teacher influenced my coaching methods as I was exposed to diverse learners... ." -Coach 8</p>
3. Employing Conflict Resolution and Prioritization Strategies	<p>–arranging schedules during conflicts</p> <p>–prioritization of tasks</p> <p>–delegating responsibilities when roles overlap</p>	<p>-conflicts;</p> <p>-prioritization;</p> <p>-activities;</p> <p>-written works;</p> <p>-structured schedule</p>	<p>"As a coach-teacher, I manage my time if my time schedule conflicts with my coaching and teaching role by arranging my schedule properly..." -Coach 1</p> <p>"..., I give activities to my students to do within that certain period of time, and then they will pass it to me for me to check if all of them will cooperate." -Coach 4</p> <p>"... I considered coaching and gave some written works or activities in my regular class so that both teaching and coaching are still on it." -Coach 5</p>

			<p>"... prioritization is the key... If a major academic deadline and an important game coincide, I work with students to ensure they manage both effectively." -Coach 6</p> <p>"Do what is most demanded for the day. Prioritize things that are of immediate need." -Coach 7</p> <p>"... prioritization, and clear communication... I create a structured schedule that allocates dedicated time for both responsibilities..." -Coach 8</p>
4. Using Institutional and Collegial Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -delegating tasks to colleagues -accessing financial, material, and human resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -support; -facilities; -equipment; -monetary; -learning activity sheets; -department head; -colleagues 	<p>"... are the facilities and equipment that they provide. ... Sometimes, they also gave monetary contributions to buy equipment." -Coach 1</p> <p>"... for my co-teachers and colleagues in our department, sometimes it is unavoidable that I cannot attend our class, so they are the ones who will give tasks to my students..." -Coach 3</p> <p>"Ok. For me is, is the, is the, aside from the financial support, ... the support is resources." -Coach 4</p> <p>"... with the help of my school and my colleagues is when I'm out for coaching, the school heads or the department heads assign available teachers or colleagues to monitor my regular classes..." -Coach 5</p>
5. Dual Role Management through Strategic Planning and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -coordinating schedules -delegating teaching tasks -utilizing clear communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -manage my schedule; -ask the help; -leave activities; -activity sheets; -prepared learning activities; 	<p>"... as a coach-teacher for example, if I have a schedule in training and at the same time I have a class, I ask the help of my co-teacher to oversee my class while I'm in training..." -Coach 1</p> <p>"..., and then we also have master</p>

		-study sessions; - flexible training; - clear communication	teachers and department heads in the department who can monitor the classes that we have left behind." -Coach 2 "..., so I just do tasks for the children and have my colleagues in our department follow up on that. That's all." -Coach 3 "... to my department head to supervise my class and to assist my class when I am coaching." - Coach 4 "... I leave learning activities sheets or tasks to do for my regular class and ask the favor of my colleagues to oversee or monitor my students." -Coach 5
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Emerging Theme 1. Effective Time Management and Scheduling

One of the participants of this study expressed that, “when you want to do more things in a day, time management is important”. As insisted by Ghafar (2024), time management is an integral part human existence. As a coach in the public school, he needs to properly manage his time effectively and efficiently perform his functions. Furthermore, time management is the process of planning how to divide your time between specific activities; effectively managing your time means work smarter, not harder (The Mind Tools Content Team, n.d.). In comparison to the definition of time management mentioned lately, this study revealed that all the participant-coach did time management and scheduling as one of their techniques in balancing their roles as teacher and coach.

Emerging Theme 2. Reciprocal Influence and Integration of Teaching and Coaching Practices

When a coach had been coaching for a quite a long time, he mastered already the processes and procedures of training. He sees already the big picture ahead of him even at the first day of training. He can determine capabilities and abilities of potential athletes and athletes that need more rigid and in-depth training. His experience will be useful when dealing with his athletes. However, the main function of a teacher includes sharing of knowledge and wisdom and honing specific life-long skills which are needed for his athlete’s existence (Navarro, 2024). On the other hand, sport coach motivates and inculcates the importance of discipline and manner towards teammates and opponents. This two-fold functions of coaching and teaching lived in one body, integration coaching to teaching or vice versa is a technique to balance both careers. In contrary, the study of Cristobal (2024) which was anchored to the Kolb’s Experiential Learning Theory, tried to examined the critical role of MAPEH (Music, Arts, Physical Education, and Health) teacher-coaches in integrating sports within the Philippine basic education system, with an emphasis on their competencies and

experiences in sports coaching. His study revealed that MAPEH teacher-coaches with robust sports experiences and certifications are significantly more effective in their coaching roles.

Meanwhile, this study sees experienced of the teacher in teaching influenced teacher's coaching methods or vice versa by sharing to the athletes what makes a good and successful athletes in the future. In reality, all participants of the study told that they are employing integration of coaching in teaching.

Emerging Theme 3. Employing Conflict Resolution and Prioritization Strategies

When conflict arises in balancing teaching and coaching roles. This needs to be addressed and resolved to better carry both functions. One of the participants of this study mentioned that, in order to avoid inconvenience to both careers, prioritization strategies must be employed. Middleton, et. al. (2018) defined in his study prioritization is a technique of identifying tasks in order of its importance. He emphasized that doing most important to less important tasks is doing prioritization technique. In addition, the study of Sajeevanie (2020) prioritization of tasks has a big impact in the academic, personal and sport life of student-athletes in State Universities in Sri Lanka. Thus, it can be said that prioritization of tasks is helpful in developing student-athletes holistic performance while conflict resolution address problem on time and schedule constraints. That is why participants of this study employed these important techniques as way of balancing their dual tasks. Among the eight (8) participants, six (6) of them employing the techniques to better carry tasks efficiently and effectively.

Emerging Theme 4. Using Institutional and Collegial Support

Collaborating with other teachers in the school is part of the life of teachers teaching in one institution. Knowing that, one institution under one agency has its one mission, vision, goals and objectives to achieve at the end of the day. These teachers may be divided with their skills and specialization but they are bound to achieve what is about to achieve. With this, they collaborate, they ask help and they need technical assistance from their mentors or the master teachers. In case of the teacher-coach in the public school, most of the time they need to leave their classes for coaching event. In this case, someone has to take over his place in his absence. This is asking collegial help. Strong and healthy collegial relationship among school teachers is regarded as an essential component of school effectiveness and teacher enhancement (Shah, 2021). In addition to that, harmonious relationship among teacher-coaches in the academe is building strong relationship. In the article published by Simons, et. al. (2022), he mentioned that relationship among employees in a small organization is tighter that in a big organization. Considering the age gap issues, different educational background and experiences, these creates barriers. However, when these employees focus on their individual tasks, they will complete tasks complimentary to others. However, extending help in your vacancy can solve problem of the organization especially the tasks left by the teacher-coach. Actually, this study identified seven (7) participants out of eight (8) to have been practicing collegial support in the Division of South Cotabato.

Emerging Theme 5. Dual Role Management Through Strategic Planning and Collaboration.

In an organization, issues and problems are natural phenomena. In an academe most issues occur in the implementation of programs, projects and activities. They may be in the form of technical issues, personal, social or work related. In the case on teacher-coach, in order to maintain both teaching and coaching careers,

there a need for a strategic planning on how to carry both roles of one so none will complain. Every teacher-coach needs to have plan to know when he is heading to. Most coaches failed without strategic planning. With strategic plan, teacher-coach may see what is crucial, how to get there, what to avoid, and what to disregard (Mohr, 2024). Furthermore, teacher-coach recognize their dual role, King (2023) insisted that strategic planning makes members of the organization proactive not reactive. This allows the group to foresee future mishaps, and when these happen, the team has already back up plans in order to keep the group marching forward. Thus, this strategic plan is seen by the participants vital in balancing dual roles. Seven (7) out of eight (8) participants dwells on the exploration of utilizing strategic planning in coaching and teaching.

Table 2. Themes on the Challenges of Coaches in Coaching Special Program in Sports Student-Athletes in Public Schools

Emerging Themes	Clustered Themes	Codes	Significant Statement
1. Time Management & Scheduling Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -managing limited training time -balancing conflicting schedules -adjusting practice schedules with academic classes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -time management; -schedules not enough; -class conflict; -limited time allotment; -not available -players is hard to find 	<p>"Ah... the training and practice schedules are not enough to facilitate and teach them." -Coach 1</p> <p>"..., especially when you're balancing class schedules with training schedules..." -Coach 3</p> <p>"... First is time management, ... There are times when my students or my athletes are not available..." -Coach 4</p>
2. Limited Resources & Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -managing budget constraints -dealing with inadequate training space and human resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -lack of equipment; -limited budgets; -lack of facilities; -funding; -resources; -uniforms; -training equipment 	<p>"... are lack of equipment, ..." -Coach 2</p> <p>"...is the lack of funding and resources. ..." -Coach 6</p> <p>"... the lack of facilities and resources to be used by the student-athletes." -Coach 8</p>
3. Student Motivation, Discipline, and Skill Development Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -addressing lack of interest -enhancing skill development -instilling discipline -motivating student-athletes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lack of interest; skills not enhanced; lack of discipline; motivation; behavior; lack of knowledge 	<p>"... some students lack interest..." -Coach 2</p> <p>"Ok. As a coach... the second is the,,,, skills. All athletes must have skills..." -Coach 4</p> <p>"... First is motivation to focus on their skills while in practice. There are some students who do not really like training; it's more about 'pa pogi,' ..." -Coach 5</p> <p>"Most of the SPS students lack focus</p>

			<p>and discipline in the classroom and have difficulties understanding theories in their specific specialization. ..."-Coach 7</p> <p>"Ahhh, sometimes it's the motivation. It's hard to motivate a child, especially if you really want to shift him or her..." -Coach 3</p>
4. Administrative and Policy Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Navigating school policies -Managing administrative requirements -balancing teaching and coaching roles -securing approvals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -school policies; -administrative requirements; -class schedule; -approval; -paper works; -regular classes 	<p>"... It's because we also handle regular classes, so it's different..." -Coach 2</p> <p>"we have new criteria and rules in DepEd that there should be 6 hours intended for teaching time and 2 hours intended for paper works or other works. ..." -Coach 3</p> <p>"..., since I am teaching regular classes and my athletes in the Special Program in Sports and their time and my time cannot be suited with each other..." -Coach 4</p> <p>"The school policies or administrative requirements create challenges for me as a coach"-Coach 5</p> <p>"... You need to secure approval for training camps..." -Coach 6</p> <p>"Not clear and inconsistent policy and interpretation of the school administration affects the coaching focus. ..." -Coach 7</p> <p>"Some school policies and administrative tasks hinder me from being a hands-on coach..." -Coach 8</p>
5. Socio-economic and Inclusion Challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -addressing financial struggles -ensuring equal opportunities -promoting inclusion and equity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -financial struggles; -cannot afford; -not privileged; -inclusion; -equity; -equal recognition; -access to competitions 	<p>"The difficulties that I've encountered... is that many athletes come from diverse backgrounds, and some have, have them,..." -Coach 6</p> <p>"Inclusion and equity challenges. Some athletes cannot receive equal recognition, opportunities, or access to different competitions compared to</p>

			mainstream athletes..." -Coach 8 "... the equipment that can be given to the students is limited, so there are students who cannot afford to buy the equipment..." -Coach 2
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Emerging Theme 1. Time Management & Scheduling Constraints

Scheduling training addresses issue on time management constraint. As coach in the public school, it is known that time is very much essential in carrying and performing tasks effectively. Being coach and at the same time teacher, planning activities of the day must be lived for. According to Samphy (2024) poor time management leads to decreased productivity, disappointing performance and procrastination. Indeed, time management and scheduling constraints continue to surface as problems among coaches in the public schools. Actually, five (5) out of eight (8) coaches experienced these issues. They emphasized that these greatly impact their training schedules. In addition to that, these have also have big contribution to poor discipline, low self-esteem and low self-improvement (Think Eleven, 2024)

Emerging Theme 2 Limited Resources and Infrastructure

Coaching has never been easy without enough playing venue or space and resources needed. In the recently approved budget for Department of Education, General Appropriation Act (GAA) allocated 793.74B (Philippine Press, 2025). This budget will be used for Basic Education Facilities (P36.81-B), Basic Education Curriculum (P3.69-B), Early Language Literacy and Numeracy (P106.23M), Physical Fitness and School Sports (P479.17M), and Implementation of the Grant of Cash allowance, Hardship Pay, and Reclassification of Positions (19.77B). The budget for Physical Fitness and School Sports will be equitably distributed to 47,831 schools in the whole country. With this big amount for the implementation of sports in school, it always turns out to be insufficient to fund the different sport events (Panaligan, 2024). This insufficiency was also experienced by many sport coaches in South Cotabato Division. Truly, eight (8) out of eight (8) mentioned their struggles in coaching with limited infrastructure and facilities. Indeed, Sport equipment, facilities and infrastructure are important for mental and physical preparation, empowering athletes with the necessary equipment, expert guidance and conducive environments to excel in their respective sports and maintain a competitive edge over their rivals (Saunders, 2023).

Emerging Theme 3. Students Motivation, Discipline and Skills Development Challenges

In the study conducted by Singh, et. al. (2021), motivation is an innate talent that is crucial in learning and training. Motivation serves as pushing element for the athletes to do better than the usual capacity of playing the sport. However, in the absence of motivation, there will no learning or there will only be little learning. On the other, discipline is the foundation of being successful in sport. Ega (2023) emphasized that discipline is not only about obeying the do's and don't's of the game but it also includes commitment, dedication and strong work ethics. In this study, students' motivation, discipline and skills development challenges were found to be one of the problems of coaches in the public school. To quantify, six (6) out of (8) coaches raised these issues during interview.

Emerging Theme 4. Administrative Policy Constraints

Most coaches in the public schools holds advisory and subjects. In the DepEd Order No.53 Series, 2024, regular teachers in the department should have six (6) hours of actual teaching hours and two (2) hours for ancillary tasks such as conducting action research, checking of test papers, encoding scores, preparation of instructional materials. With this nature of the job of the teachers, they hardly manage time to train or coach athletes. In the study of Pandey, et. al. (2023), this administrative constraint had been affecting the performance of teachers to do coaching. This disallows them to conduct training within the (8) hours of duty. This scenario made practice and training after eight (8) hours of duty so that classes will not be hampered and learning continues. However, when athletic meet is past approaching, coaches must focus with their coaching career. They need to have whole day training in preparation for the meet. Forro (2024) insisted that in the absence of the teacher who coaches sport, some teachers must take over his class especially those who are vacant. This scenario was testified by the coaches. Out of (8) coaches who underwent interview by the researcher seven (7) from them experience this struggle in coaching, the administrative policy constraint.

Emerging Theme 5. Socio-Economic and Inclusion Challenges

Socio-economic challenge was raised by three (3) out of (8) participants during the interview of the researcher. In the journal published by Sajid, et. al. (2018), socio-economic constraint is a factor that impedes the athletes and coaches to thrive in their sport. Sport that entails monetary consideration. In order for the coaches and athletes to sustain training, limited resources such as equipment and facilities are sometimes shouldered by them. Thus, playing sport still needs financial support even in the public schools. In the training conducted by Sto. Nino National High School for their Special Program in Sport athletes, they are actually providing their personal sport equipment such badminton racket, shuttlecock and net. This occurrence is normal in the public school. That is why, when one join sport, money talks.

Table 2. Themes on the Triumphs of Coaches in Coaching Special Program in Sports Student-Athletes in Public Schools

Emerging Temes	Clustered Themes	Codes	Significant Statements
1.Competitive Success and Achievement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> –achieving wins in competitions –reaching higher meets –qualifying for major events 	winning; higher meets; competition; qualify; represent	<p>“Ahhmm, for me, is, of course, winning! I can consider that my greatest achievement was winning. ...” -Coach 4</p> <p>“... may mga students kami n nakapunta or qualified sa higher meets like SRAA From Municipal meet, provincial Meet at saka SRAA Meet. ...” -Coach 2</p> <p>“Of course, it feels good when you see your athlete succeed in his chosen</p>

			<p>sport. For example, he won a Palaro or became part of the Philippine Team." -Coach 3</p> <p>"... is my players competed at the Municipal Meet and Provincial Meet, and now representing the school for the Regional or SRAA Meet." -Coach 4</p>
2. Holistic Athlete Development and Personal Growth	<p>–imparting knowledge and discipline</p> <p>–inspiring positive attitudes and character</p> <p>–enhancing confidence and personal growth</p> <p>–fostering a positive, inclusive environment</p>	<p>-knowledge;</p> <p>-skills;</p> <p>-discipline;</p> <p>-attitude;</p> <p>-spiritual;</p> <p>-confidence;</p> <p>-growth;</p> <p>-environment</p>	<p>"Ah, my greatest achievement in terms of sports and teaching Programs is to impart my knowledge, skills, and good discipline to my student-athlete ..." - Coach 1</p> <p>"Ahhmm, besides the technical aspects, so of course, their attitude. The attitude of the children ... for the children to achieve their goals or win competitions." -Coach 3</p> <p>"... is guiding my student-athletes on how to fight their emotion during the tournaments. Especially if they are the champions, it is my greatest achievement." -Coach 5</p>
3. Innovative Coaching Practices Leading to Success	<p>–implementing personalized training plans</p> <p>–adopting new drills and strategies</p> <p>–enforcing discipline and team-building</p> <p>–utilizing data-driven analysis</p>	<p>-strategies; drills;</p> <p>-individual training;</p> <p>-personalized;</p> <p>-data-driven;</p> <p>-mental conditioning;</p> <p>-team-building</p>	<p>"... For example, I let them jog for 15 minutes before doing some drills to develop and improve their endurance." -Coach 1</p> <p>"..., is 'yong sa drills Ma'am, sa drills. It's because that's where they improve their skills, their stamina, their power, their agility in their play." -Coach 2</p> <p>"... because in coaching, you have to be firm, and the child you're teaching has to know how to follow the rules..." -Coach 3</p> <p>"..., for example, on how to set a ball on a tekong for them to spike in the right position and will be delivered in a good kick while the ball is on play." - Coach 5</p> <p>"Yes, Ma'am. I implemented individual training plans. Not all</p>

			<p>athletes on my team have the same abilities. ..." -Coach 6</p> <p>"For me, teaching discipline first before knowledge, skills, and techniques is my best strategy." -Coach 7</p> <p>"...including personalized training plans intended for individual strengths and weaknesses, mental conditioning techniques to build resilience and confidence, and team-building exercises to enhance communication within the team. ..." -Coach 8</p>
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Emerging Theme 1. Competitive Success and Achievement

Seeing athletes going up the stage and receive their recognition as winner simply boosts coach’s confidence and esteem. Experiencing winning in sport undoubtedly increases self-confidence and builds self-competence and positive self-image (Editorial Team, 2024). Furthermore, winning also reinforces coach’s thought that he is capable of making something bigger and better. In relation to this study, six (6) out of eight (8) participants of the study expressed that they felt competitive success and achievement after bringing athletes to higher competitions such as regional and even national level. In the recently concluded 2025 Soccsksargen Region Athletic Association Meet, South Cotabato bagged the most gold medals putting itself to be the overall champion during the SRAA Meet. Thus, most coaches of the Division will be moving towards more rigid training and practice. This is in preparation of the National Athletic Association Meet in Vigan, Ilocos Sur this summer. This winning moment of the Division made the coaches and athletes more persistent and motivated to win the national trophy (Forro, 2025).

Emerging Theme 2. Holistic Athlete Development and Personal Growth

Being enrolled in the Special Program in Sports, this program does not only develop students’ playing attitude and skills. Schools offering the program have a curriculum that does not focus only in sports but offers an optimal holistic development. In the study conducted by Thompson, et. al. (2022), they found out that sports school student-athletes receive considerable support in terms of academic and athletic services, more intensified training and competition schedules with high-level training partners, but regularly miss school. Moreover, the study of Lee (2022) proposed an integral conceptual model to enhance the holistic development of sport-based development initiative as a road map of Singapore in its vision, Vision 2030: Live Better through Sport. However, Thompson, et. al. (2022) also discovered that here are a multitude of immediate, short- and long-term positive impacts associated with the academic/vocational, athletic/physical, psychosocial and psychological development of sports school student-athletes. To verify this finding of

Thompson, et. al. (2022), this study openly admitted that 75% or 6 out of 8 participants developed their student-athletes not only physical but other aspects of the life such as emotional, social and mental.

Emerging Theme 3. Innovative Coaching Practices Leading to Success

Teaching and coaching are two separate roles of teachers in the school. Eight (8) hours is intended for teaching, while coaching is done after teaching career in a day. While coaching is also important as coaching, teachers innovate coaching practices. Hodge (2018) suggested that teacher-coach may innovate coaching practices to maximize the impact of his coaching. Teacher-coach may nurture trust among his athletes.. This gives him the assurance and confidence that training is still going even in his absence. Another is building credibility. Words are enough for detailed instruction. Any statement coming from the mouth of the coach should be all credible and must be stood for all time because a wise man has only one word after all. Moreover, Valenzuela (2022) pointed out that, a coach needs to pinpoint weaknesses from his athletes to directly address the issue. This is to determine which among the needed skills needs to be improved or honed. Such actions are evidently mentioned by the participants of this study. 88% or almost all the participants innovated their coaching career due to time constraints.

Conclusion

Based on the synthesized emerging themes summarized in the study's findings, conclusions were drawn.

The study concluded that balancing coaching and teaching careers continues to be implemented through proper time management, integrating best practices in teaching and coaching roles, prioritization, asking for collegial support, and strategic planning for better dual-role implementation.

Moreover, teachers who are coaching sports share the same challenging experiences in time management, limited resources and equipment, discipline and character, policy constraints, and socio-economic challenges. These challenges have affected student-athletes and coaches' performance in training and competition. Despite these challenges, teacher coaches still find silver lining behind these onerous and arduous tasks. They also find triumphs in every student-athletes success, such as winning in competition, personal growth, and character development, and continue finding ways to innovate coaching and teaching careers. Finally, as frontline staff, teachers are the immediate contact of the learners. Thus,

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